

The Rise and Fall of Isis in Iraq and: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (Isis) caused a disastrous collision in the region. Now Isis is destroyed especially in Iraq as the military forces along-with coalition forces successfully counteracted against their insurgency. This paper discussed the origins, agenda and resurgence possibilities of Daesh in Iraq. By keeping in view the efforts made by the Iraqi army and confederates, this study assumed that government and military officials need to take actions against any potential resurgence in future. After US military withdrawal from Syria, the Iraqi government are concerned about security and control of the region. Therefore, it is suggested that sustained local action can help to fight against post-Isis activities. Additionally, Iraq and Syria should also alleviate internal conflicts so that Isis may not get any probability to return.

KEYWORDS

Isis, Iraqi Military, Islamic State of Iraq and Syria, Kurdistan, Al-Qaeda

1. INTRODUCTION

The Islamic State of Iraq and Syria, chiefly known as Isis invaded Iraq and conquered Samara, Ramadi, Mosul, Tikrit, Fajullah and other significant areas of northern Iraq in January 2014. Isis seized around 56000 kilometres of areas having 4.5 million human population. On June 2014 Abu-Mohammad Al-Adnani, the spokesperson and the senior leader of Isis released an audio media declaring their dominance as “Caliphate” and Abu Bakker Al-Baghdadi as the Calipha and the leader of the Muslims. (O’Driscoll, 2019) stated that Isis is fighting under Maoist Protracted warfare, they have learned much from the collapse and success of Al-Qaeda. Many other jihadist groups besides Al-Qaeda are existing in Yemen, Somalia and Bali are a constant threat for the tranquillity and security of the world

During the invasion, Isis also captured weapons, oil refineries and military armaments. As in June 2014, Isis captured Baiji, a city in Northern Iraq with 2,000,000 inhabitants and containing largest oil refinery. Non-state militants fired the courthouse and police station also freed prisoners from Baiji prison. On 18th June 2014, Isis invaded the oil refinery with heavy weapons and mortars. They warned 250 guards to withdraw from the refinery and captured more than 75% of the oil refinery after heavy bloodshed (Hashemi, 2016). Also, Isis militants invaded Turkish consulate and abducted their head with 45 other staff members. According to (Abouzeid, 2018), the Isis released a footage in which they revealed weapons and artillery of Iraqi army confirmed that these weapons will help them to fuel the war on both sides of the border. Majority of weapons

captured by Isis plundered from Al-Qyara base Mosul during their attack. Ammunition, assault weapons and rockets of mass destruction were captured by Isis during their invasion. According to (Gunter, 2013), Isis carried out several attacks on innocent people in Iraq leading the genocide of many tribes. These crimes since 2014, include both war crimes and human rights violation. So-called Islamic jihadists have overtaken most of the states in Iraq and Syria and slaughtered thousands of civilians. They promised to spread this terror all over the Middle East and beyond (Reseat Doc 2014). A report presented by (Crawford, 2018) revealed that the Isis capacity to attacks dropped from an average of 208 to 121 in January 2019. This is because of losing territorial control in most of the cities due to joint military operation against Isis in Syria and Most of the activities by Isis are being procured where local tribes are working under the flag of Isis causing violence and destruction in many areas.

Iraq has always been under certain war conditions. Great Iraqi revolution (1920), Iraqi-Shia revolts (1935- 1936), Iraq-Iran war (1980-1988), Kuwait-Iraq war (Gulf war 1990-1991), Iraq-Kurdish civil war (1995-1996), and others. In 2003, U.S invaded Iraq and overthrew of Saddam Hossain's regime. This war took very long to get ended as many small native Iraqi militant groups raised and forced their government to persuade external forces for their withdrawal. During the U.S-Iraq conflict, around 600,000 Iraqi got killed during the first four years of war. However, in 2009 U.S military withdrew but still many remained there as hired by private companies and government officials to cope with the potential threat. In 2014, U.S military again re-involved in Iraq against Isis and in 2017, finally with Iraqi military defeated Isis militants and conquered the civil war. However, despite the massive success in Iraq, the threat concerning even more powerful rise of Isis is still looming. As (For, 2013) stated the disagreement about joint actions against Isis can lead Baghdad and Erbil to massive destruction. Although this group has lost much of its control there are chances that they may against overcome the forces due to their disputes and ever-existing disagreements. According to (Mordi, 2015), General of US Defense Department reported that there are diverse opinions about Isis's current state, however, it is said that they have grown their weapons and military power as compared to earlier times. Defense Intelligence Agency (DIA) and Combines Joint Task Force (CJTF) claimed that Isis have reduced their activities but recently both agencies assessed that Isis has now more than 30,000 non-state militants ready to invade Iraq's ungoverned areas (Abdel-Razek & Puttick, 2016).

2. GENESIS & RISE OF ISIS IN IRAQ:

Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS) or Islamic State of Iraq and Levant (ISIL) is a non-state Islamic militant group which has the Salafi Sunni doctrine. This non-state militant group originated in 1999 but initially, it was a small unpopular group until 2014 when they took control over Iraq. Earlier named as Jama'at al-Tawhid wal-Jihad it is also known as an Islamic State in Al-sham which is an ancient name of this region and the group claims that its goal is to create regime under a Muslim ruler labelled as "Calipha". In Iraq, Isis remained as small mainly autonomous guerilla units spread in most ungoverned areas including deserts, mountains and deserts. Isis militants prey on rural areas targeting governmental officials, military persons and common people. Initially, they began with small attacks and gradually started major attacks resulting in massive warfare.

Talking mainly about the organization of Isis, it is much influenced by a proper organizational structure containing both with internal and external structure. According to (Heinrich, 2015), Isis have quite different techniques to dominate in both Iraq and Syria. Isis is mainly known for its barbaric ideologies and strategies that have troubled many tribes and regimes. Isis believes that the Muslims from the whole world should unite under the flag of Muslim caliph. As in Syria, along-with small ethnic groups Isis made agreements to start mutual interest-based war activities. While in Iraq, by directly targeting the military and government Isis to take over and captured main cities of Iraq (Hashemi, 2016).

Likewise, internally Isis runs on financial donations by its members and externally,

connected to the world the way Al-Qaeda used to interact (through audio/videos messages). Also, Isis is deeply interlinked with Al-Qaeda as world's three most prominent Islamic non-state militant group leaders Osama-Bin-Laden, Abu-Bakkar Al-Baghdadi ad Aimen al-Zawahiri all had the same doctrines and aims to forcibly implement sharia laws in the Middle east and related state. These groups were so-called jihadist, extremely violent and they worked with strong ties of brotherhood. Figure 1 graphically represents the Isis activites in Iraq

(Zaheer, 2019)

Although their strategies and techniques were different their goals and enemies were the same. According to (Mansour, 2017), both Al-Qaeda and Isis believed in the caliphate, that assumes the Islamic state under a Muslim ruler mainly knows as Caliphate. In October 2013, both Al –Zawahiri and Al-Baghdadi met in Jordan to plan their future strategies. They decided to send their fighters in Egypt to fight against the new military government in Egypt but their meeting did not result in any influential decisions. Although, both organizations believe in brotherhood and same goals but their disagreement on many matters remained prominent. However, Al-Qaeda declared to cut ties with Isis for its violent and anti-human ideologies. Conflicts these groups raised when Al-Qaeda asked Isis to withdraw its militants from Syria but Isis refused which helped other small non-state militant groups to strengthen the alliance with Isis (Revkin, 2018). (Gunter, 2013) stated that differences in strategies, policies, funding sources did not affect the brotherhood and common goals between Al-Qaeda and Isis. They reconciled, reunited and agreed on common interests. According to (Lypp, 2016), if Isis and Al-Q1aeda reconcile and reunite, it would be an alarming situation for the world. Their strategies and technique are different but their goal is the same and this time it can be Europe from where they intimate their terrorist activities. Both Al-Qaeda and Isis are conducting meetings which are helping them to reunite and work to attain the same goals. The Russian government also indicated that the signs of reunion between Al-

Qaeda and Isis show that they are going to emerge again but this time they will be united and more powerful. All the other minor terrorist organization around the world might join them as well and the consequences will be more fatal than earlier (Mearsheimer, 1994).

3. MEASURES TAKEN TO ERADICATE ISIS:

Iraqi military with coalition forces launched many operations against Isis causing severe damage to non-state militant groups. Further, Iraqis from other parts of the world also returned and joined military action. (Wilson Center, 2019) reported that many people flew from different parts of the world to join military action Isis in Iraq. Despite confronting the war front, they are surprisingly relaxed. They are from 57 different countries aims for the same purpose joining military action and helping to fight for Iraq. Iraqi military along-with Kurdish and foreign alliance took certain defensive steps against Isis. Initially, Iraqi militants were comparatively weak but later their strategies helped them to take over the control. In this regard, Iran sent General Qasim Soleimani commanding general of Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps' Quds Force (IRGC-QF) to help Iraqi military against Isis. Later this month, Iran also began to fly drones to spy secret movements of Isis members. Iranian military also sent jets to invade Isis pockets and F4 Phantom II fighters heavily bombed Isis in Iraq. In August 2014, the British military sent Tornado GR4 jets to RAF Akrotiri to heavily harm Isis in Iraq. Later, after authorizing airstrikes in Iraq, British prime minister David Cameron also asked for airstrikes against Daesh in Syria. On September (2014), the Dutch government also declared to take part in military action Isis and sent F-16 fighter jets to bomb ISIL. In October 2014, Australian prime minister Tony Abbott approved for RAAF Boeing F/A-18F Super Hornet to start airstrikes Isis in Iraq causing heavy damage to Isis military force. Similarly, Jordan, Moroccan and French military also took part in joint military action against Isis causing serious damage to them. However, Jordanian pilot Muath al-Kasasbeh was executed as his jet was rashed in Syria and burnt to death by Isis (Ali, 2015).

Furthermore, Operation Inherent Resolve initiated by the US with the Iraqi military which was a combined joint task against Isis in both Iraq and Syria. This military operation started in June 2015 and continued as the threat is yet not over. U.S military with France, Britain, Turkey, Canada, Netherlands and other allies began this operation to support the local allies. About 80% attacks have been carried out against Isis in this operation and finally in March 2019 US and allies liberated 110.000 square kilometres and 7.7 million from the so-called Islamic State or Daesh.

According to (Lindsay Church, 2016), a close collaboration between the Iraqi government, Iraqi Army, Peshmerga forces, US military and other international forces have successfully defeated Isis in almost all the occupies areas. This huge collaboration has not only befitted Iraq also; it led successful action against removing Isis militants from most parts of Syria. On October 2014, Canadian Prime Minister Stephan Harper declared that the Canadian military will join coalition forces in Iraq and sent nine aircraft to take part against Isis in joint military airstrikes. This military action was later named as Operation Impact and during the same year, the Canadian Parliament voted to extend the mission in Syria. During the joint military strike against Isis, Canadian forces heavily massacred the Isis militants and successfully weaken their control over Iraq (Al-qarawee, 2014). In 2015, Russian and Syrian forces heavily bombed Isil in Al Nusra

causing severe damage. Right after the airstrikes, Isis started losing control in Iraq and Syria which helped the Local militants and allies to launch more airstrikes against Isis. Further, at the end of 2017, civil war against Isis in Iraq ended and the Iraqi government declared the death of Isis and reestablished their lost governmental control. However, Syria was still under warfare situation where Isis was gradually moving towards defeat. Similarly, other allies including Turkey, Australia, Denmark and others attacked the Isis in Iraq caused massive destruction against them which eventually collapsed in 2017 but many military forces are still in Iraq to counteract against any future invasion (Katzman & Humud, 2016).

4. PREVALENT ISIS THREAT IN IRAQ & IMPEDIMENTS IN CONTAINING ISIS:

Now that Isis has also got defeated in Syria as a result of joint efforts by the Syrian military, Kurd militia and foreign alliances. The Battle of Baghuz Fawqani, which started in February 2019 containing massive airstrikes, artillery and strong coalition, Isis faced a huge loss (Abouzeid, 2018). On February 9th, 2019 The Syrian Democratic Force (SDF) seized two kilometres area having 41 important points and successfully repelled Isis attack. SDF and coalition forces made significant efforts despite extreme weather and dust storms. On 16th February SDF commander, Jiya Furat stated that the Isis have emptied most of the seized area and government forces will declare their success in a few days. On February 26, 2019, many members of Isis surrendered with their families and in April 2019, Isis leader Abu-Bakkar Al-Baghdadi declared their massive defeat in Syria (Sayej, 2019).

However, during Baghdadi's video release, he also declared that Isis will regain lost control. Also, he warned about Isis existence in Libya and the next invasion will be more brutal than ever (Al-qarawee, 2014). According to (Gunter, 2013), despite breaking down Isis in Iraq and Syria, it is now reorganized and comparatively more powerful than earlier. Although they are lacking funds to continue their activities, they have not lost complete control rather they are nourishing and uniting with local non-state militant groups which are a greater risk for Iraq and Syria. (Mordi, 2015) stated that new strategies and activities are constantly threatening Iraq that they will again rise and this time they will be more powerful and strategic. Despite their heavy loss, it is clear that they will keep on rising in ungoverned areas of Iraq and Kurdistan. According to (Revkin, 2018), after the physical demise of Isis still, their activities are continued. They are existing, meetings are secretly being held and we cannot the persistent threat of their second invasion as Isis is killed but the members and the jihadist group still exist. (Taneja, 2018) also sees re-emergence of Isis as he stated that jihadists groups are ready to reappear and authorities also confirmed that many unknown militants are travelling from fake passports that raises serious security concerns in the region.

At the government level, weak institutions and especially the head of the state had weak control over far-flung areas where Isis nourished and invaded. (Lypp, 2016) argued that

the main reason behind Isis control over Iraq is weak management. These non-state militants are not ordinary trained men rather they are advanced and internationally trained terrorist possessing powerful skills and weapons that are bringing massive destruction and growing their power every day with command and control capabilities. (Gerges, 2017) also affirmed that Isis selected far-flung areas of Iraq to invade where security is comparatively weak. Also, their agenda was to expand their control over other states interlinked with Iraq so that they chose the Western part of Syria. Isis invasion in Iraq led to serious concerns regarding security and military control. According to (Wilson Center, 2019), after the Iraq-US war, the Iraqi government has always been struggling. Similarly, the Iraqi government failed to support Sunnis which later preferred to support Isis. In 2013, many Sunnis protested against the government in Fajullah, Ramadi, Kirkuk, Mosul and Samara. They raised voice against Iraqi Prime minister Nuri Al-Maliki's Shia dominated government causing conflicts between Sunnis and Kurds. Furthermore, the Iraqi military was also lacking certain war skills as according to (Mansour, 2017), when Iraqi military declared operation against Isis invasion they could not fight because of several reasons. They had insufficient troops, lack of military discipline, warfare planning and weapons. (Henderson, 2018) argued that despite having US military aid and equipment, the Iraqi military could not retaliate. Weak strategies and discipline led them to surrender but later they fought back and defeated Isis. Figure 2 (Klosi, 2021)

5. CONCLUSION:

With the help of Allied forces and by using Egypt provided by them, Iraq and its armed forces have been successful in defeating ISIS in Iraq. Isis and its allies are physically dead. Iraqi military with coalition forces has effectively demolished their insurgency. Isis is down in both Iraq and Syria but not completely demolished. They are still in action but geographically circumscribed. Although, Isis has been badly defeated still they are a threat for global peace and solidarity. After demolishing their so-called Caliphate, they have ceased the war but they are a constant danger for the whole region. Keeping it down requires disciplined and subtle efforts. Current tensions between the US and Iraq can benefit Isis to increase their power.

Iraq and Syrian have paid much due to Isis insurgency in the past few years. It is a constant threat for both countries and if they manage to regroup, outcomes will be even more horrible. Keeping ISIS weak and Isolated can help to avoid any insurgency in future. Similarly, avoiding the conflict situation in Iraq will also help to keep Isis disrupted. The Iraqi government needs to sustain friendly relationships with its allies especially Kurd Militia. Both Iraq and Syria needs to keep Isis insurgents calm and powerless by cutting off their financial chains and relations with other non-militant groups. As predicted by many military officials and intelligence agencies, Isis will resurge again with even more force and violence, the threat is still looming in Iraq. It is important to counteract against every existing non-state militant group in the region. The resurgence needs to be countered with a bigger resolve and commitment by the Iraqis themselves as the drawdown of foreign forces will deny them the access to latest weapons, equipment and training they had a few years ago.

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